

TABLE 2—ESR SPECTRAL DATA OF Cu^{II} COMPLEXES

Compd.	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{ave}	G	K_{\parallel}^2	K_{\perp}^2	λ_0 cm ⁻¹	λ cm ⁻¹
Cu(L) ₂ (OAC) ₂	2.23	2.05	2.17	4.77	0.64	0.53	-828	-526
Cu(L ₁) ₂ (OAC) ₂	2.19	2.04	2.14	4.98	0.52	0.42	-828	-434

⁴T_{1g} (G) and ⁶A_{1g} (S) → ⁴T_{2g} (G) transitions respectively. Based on these results, high-spin octahedral geometry has been proposed for the complexes. The Pd^{II} complexes are diamagnetic and they show two peaks around 15 100 and 17 300 assignable respectively to the transitions, ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2g} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g} of square-planar geometry. The Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are also diamagnetic. These complexes, based on their elemental analysis, conductance and ir spectral data, have been assigned tetrahedral geometry—the most preferred one for them.

The esr parameters calculated for the Cu^{II} complexes are listed in Table 2. There is not much difference between esr spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes at room temperature and at liquid nitrogen temperature. The complexes show two peaks, one of very low intensity and the other of high intensity, from which g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} values have been calculated. The g_{\parallel} values are less than 2.3 indicating covalent character of the metal-ligand bond⁹. The axial symmetry parameter (G) is greater than 4 suggesting no interaction between the copper centres in solid state. The complexes are of out-of-plane π -bonded type since K_{\parallel}^2 values are greater than K_{\perp}^2 values. The spin-orbit coupling constant for the complexes (λ) is less than that for the free metal ion (λ_0), suggesting considerable mixing of ground and excited terms.

The Mössbauer spectrum of Fe^{III}-ACTS shows a moderately resolved six-line pattern with an isomer shift (δ) of 0.58 mm s⁻¹ and a quadrupole splitting (ΔE_q) of 1.66 mm s⁻¹. The δ value observed is in the range reported for high-spin Fe^{III} octahedral complexes¹⁰. The ΔE_q value is, however, higher and this may be due to the lower symmetry of the complex¹⁰.

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Palladium(II) Chloride Complexes of some Aryl Methyl Sulphides. Synthesis and their Electronic Spectral Studies

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THE electronic spectra of the complexes of PdCl₂ with methyl phenyl sulphide and *o*-, *m*- and *p*-tolyl methyl sulphides have been studied^{1,2} both in solid state and in solutions and characterised for trans-structure. Molecular orbital diagram for the PdCl₂-(methyl phenyl sulphide)₂ complex has been developed to interpret the most intense bands as electron-transfer transitions. In the present investigation several mono-, di- and trisubstituted phenyl methyl sulphides and their PdCl₂ complexes have been prepared and their electronic spectra have been analysed to study the substituent effects over the charge transfer bands.

Palladium(II) chloride treated with a few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid was dissolved in water (10 ml). The solution was mixed with the required amount of the ligand in ethanol (70 ml). In all the cases 0.05 mol of PdCl₂ was mixed with 0.1 mol of the ligand. The mixture was then shaken well for a few minutes and left for 1 h; in some cases,

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TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES AND LIGANDS

Compd.	Colour	M.p.* °C	Analysis % :		λ_{max} nm	ϵ	Ligand spectra**	
			Found/(Calcd.)				λ_{max} nm	ϵ
			C	H				
$PdCl_2(C_6H_5SCH_3)_2$	Intense yellow	119–20 ^a	39.77 (39.48)	3.82 (3.79)	332 277	11 600 7 100	277	910
$PdCl_2(o-ClC_6H_4SCH_3)_2$	Yellowish brown	214–15 ^b	33.89 (33.93)	2.88 (2.84)	328 277	11 500 9 500	286 279	1 300 1 350
$PdCl_2(m-ClC_6H_4SCH_3)_2$	Orange red	147–48 ^c	34.32 (33.93)	2.92 (2.84)	330 277	11 900 8 600	275	1 900
$PdCl_2(p-ClC_6H_4SCH_3)_2$	Intense yellow	172–73 ^a	33.66 (33.93)	3.08 (2.84)	340 277	11 700 7 500	278	2 200
$PdCl_2(o-BrC_6H_4SCH_3)_2$	Orange red	220–21 ^c	29.2 (28.80)	2.40 (2.42)	328 277	9 800 7 500	286 279	1 700 1 900
$PdCl_2(m-BrC_6H_4SCH_3)_2$	Orange yellow	169–70 ^c	28.90 (28.80)	2.36 (2.42)	332 277	12 300 8 200	276	2 500
$PdCl_2(p-BrC_6H_4SCH_3)_2$	Bright yellow	166–67 ^a	28.96 (28.80)	2.62 (2.42)	342 277	12 600 7 600	278	2 200
$PdCl_2(o-IC_6H_4SCH_3)_2$	Yellow	194–95 ^c	24.84 (24.79)	1.95 (2.08)	326 277	8 000 8 700	288 279	1 700 2 000
$PdCl_2(m-IC_6H_4SCH_3)_2$	Yellow	169–70 ^c	24.68 (24.79)	2.18 (2.08)	332 277	11 600 9 500	277	3 500
$PdCl_2(p-IC_6H_4SCH_3)_2$	Bright yellow	186–87 ^a	24.62 (24.79)	2.20 (2.08)	350 277	12 600 7 600	281	5 500
$PdCl_2(o-NO_2C_6H_4SCH_3)_2$	Yellow	245 ^d (d)	32.52 (32.60)	2.74 (2.78)	367 277	3 100 3 200	370 278	3 600 3 600
$PdCl_2(m-NO_2C_6H_4SCH_3)_2$	Dark yellow	175–76 ^c	32.37 (32.60)	2.65 (2.78)	326 277	10 700 14 000	348 278	1 100 2 200
$PdCl_2(p-NO_2C_6H_4SCH_3)_2$	Yellow	162–63 ^c	32.51 (32.60)	2.80 (2.78)	337 277	12 800 9 900	338 275	15 300 3 600
$PdCl_2(p-COCH_3C_6H_4SCH_3)_2$	Yellowish brown	165–66 ^c	42.69 (42.42)	3.92 (3.95)	339 306 277	12 750 15 400 15 300	305 274	20 200 10 500
$PdCl_2(o-CH_3C_6H_4SCH_3)_2$	Orange red	141–42 ^a	42.50 (42.35)	4.60 (4.44)	340 277	9 750 5 700	275	1 200
$PdCl_2(m-CH_3C_6H_4SCH_3)_2$	Dark red	133–34 ^c	42.41 (42.35)	4.55 (4.44)	335 277	11 900 6 600	276	1 600
$PdCl_2(p-CH_3C_6H_4SCH_3)_2$	Yellow	158–59 ^a	42.17 (42.35)	4.56 (4.44)	344 277	12 500 6 300	276	1 400
$PdCl_2(2,6-di-CH_3C_6H_3SCH_3)_2$	Yellow	199–200 ^a	45.21 (44.88)	5.48 (5.62)	327 277	11 800 5 900	275	1 470
$PdCl_2(o-OCH_3C_6H_4SCH_3)_2$	Orange	204–205 ^e	39.07 (39.57)	4.00 (4.15)	360 306 256 ^f	2 250	287 253 ^g	320 600
$PdCl_2(m-OCH_3C_6H_4SCH_3)_2$	Orange yellow	146–47 ^c	39.29 (39.57)	4.10 (4.15)	328 277	9 300 10 400	284	2 100
$PdCl_2(p-OCH_3C_6H_4SCH_3)_2$	Orange red	164–65 ^f	40.41 (39.57)	4.36 (4.15)	365 277	10 000 6 800	294 276	630 850
$PdCl_2(o-OHC_6H_4SCH_3)_2$	Orange	124–25 ^g	37.34 (37.04)	3.53 (3.52)	362 ^h 286 256	2 200 8 100 13 700		
$PdCl_2(p-OHC_6H_4SCH_3)_2$	Orange	217–18 ^g	37.40 (37.04)	3.20 (3.52)	363 ^h 256	9 200 16 400	290 256	1 170 7 050
$PdCl_2(o-COOHC_6H_4SCH_3)_2$	Orange yellow	239–40 ^c	37.10 (37.41)	3.25 (3.14)	325 256	20 900 44 400	327 ⁱ 257	2 700 6 200
$PdCl_2(m-COOHC_6H_4SCH_3)_2$	Orange yellow	240 ^c (d)	37.42 (37.41)	3.17 (3.14)	324 256	11 300 15 800	315 ^j 258	1 400 7 800
$PdCl_2(p-COOHC_6H_4SCH_3)_2$	Orange	217–18 ^g	37.26 (37.41)	3.30 (3.14)	295 256	22 950 23 900	295 ^j 254	17 100 14 100
$PdCl_2(4-OCH_3-3-CH_3C_6H_3SCH_3)_2$	Orange	135–36 ^h	42.35 (42.08)	4.53 (4.68)	372 277	10 800 8 700	284 276	1 330 1 460
$PdCl_2(3,5-di-CH_3-4-OCH_3C_6H_2SCH_3)_2$	Yellow	158–59 ^l	44.11 (44.33)	5.10 (5.17)	356 277	10 400 5 700	276	6 730

*Solvent for crystallisation: ^aCCl₄, ^bC₆H₆–CCl₄, ^cAcOH, ^dacrylonitrile–EtOH, ^eCCl₄–EtOH, ^fCHCl₃–CCl₄, ^gC₆H₆–pet. ether, ^hMeOH, ⁱEtOH.

**In C₆H₆, except ^j in AcOH.

the solutions were kept overnight. Intense yellow, orange or orange-red crystals were separated out. The product was filtered off, washed with ethanol and recrystallised from suitable solvents (Table 1).

The solutions of the complexes in acetone and nitrobenzene were found non-conducting and diamagnetic in nature, which indicate the square-planar³ nature of the complexes in solution.

Experimental

Palladium(II) chloride (Johnson Mathey) was used. Benzene (AnalaR) was purified by freezing and then distilling over phosphorous pentoxide and glacial acetic acid (B.D.H.) was distilled over potassium permanganate. The electronic spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 554 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

In the electronic spectra a common band appears at 277 nm for all the complexes recorded in benzene, whereas in acetic acid this band appears at 256 nm without affecting the charge transfer band. Each complex exhibits two bands, one for intra-ligand transition and the other due to ligand-to-metal or metal-to-ligand charge transfer transition. The band at 277 nm in benzene and that at 256 nm in acetic acid are assigned as $L(\pi) \rightarrow L(\pi)^*$ transition. The other intense band is assigned as ligand-to-metal or metal-to-ligand charge transfer band. Appearance of these two bands at $6\,000\text{--}9\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in C_6H_6 and at $10\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in AcOH shows that they are in *trans*-configuration and the observed data are in good agreement with the reported spectral studies^{1,3,4}.

The large bathochromic shifts of the charge transfer bands (332 nm to 363 and 365 nm) in the complexes *trans*-PdCl₂(*p*-OH.C₆H₄.SCH₃)₂ and *trans*-PdCl₂(*p*-OCH₃.C₆H₄.SCH₃)₂ are due to the presence of electron-repelling OH and OCH₃ groups in *para*-position of the ligand. The shift is more in *trans*-PdCl₂(4-OCH₃-3-CH₃.C₆H₃.SCH₃)₂ than in *trans*-PdCl₂(4-OCH₃-3-CH₃.C₆H₃.SCH₃)₂ and exerts an accelerating influence of the conjugation of methoxy group with the phenyl ring. The probability of attaining planarity of methoxy group with aromatic ring increases due to the presence of methyl group at 3-position. There can, therefore, be enhanced resonance interaction of the methoxy group with the aromatic ring, resulting in a greater mesomeric electron release to the sulphur of SCH₃. Similar trend was also observed⁵ with chloramine-T oxidation of phenyl methyl sulphoxides. Bathochromic shifts are also observed in the *p*-Cl, *p*-Br and *p*-I substituted complexes. This is obviously due to the presence of SCH₃ in *para*-position to Cl, Br and I groups. Here, SCH₃ is an electron-acceptor and there is a possibility of the expansion of the valence shell of sulphur atom. Similar observation was reported⁶ in the nmr studies of some substituted phenyl methyl sulphides. The charge transfer bands of the complexes, *trans*-PdCl₂(*o*-NO₂.C₆H₄.SCH₃)₂, *trans*-PdCl₂(*p*-NO₂.C₆H₄.SCH₃)₂, *trans*-PdCl₂(*o*-COOH.C₆H₄.SCH₃)₂ and *trans*-PdCl₂(*p*-COOH.C₆H₄.SCH₃)₂ and those of the ligand bands absorb almost at the same frequency. In such case the directional charge transfer might have been opposed by the electron-withdrawing nature of these substituents in the phenyl ring. The OCH₃, NO₂ and COOH groups in *meta*-position cause hypsochromic

shift due to the electron-withdrawing effect. Methoxy group in *ortho*-position causes a bathochromic shift due to enhanced resonance which outweighs its inductive effect. Two CH₃ groups cause steric inhibition in *trans*-PdCl₂(2,6-di-CH₃.C₆H₃.SCH₃)₂ complex which results in hypsochromic shift. The symmetry of sulphur *p*-orbitals requires that in the polar excited form of methyl sulphide, the sulphur-methyl single bond should lie in the same plane as the benzene ring. *Ortho*-substituents would therefore be expected to inhibit sulphur-benzene conjugation. Steric inhibition of resonance is also observed in *trans*-PdCl₂(3,5-di-CH₃-4-OCH₃.C₆H₂.SCH₃)₂.

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Polarographic Study on the Complexation of Praseodymium with some Amino Acids

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THE present study reports the stability constants of the Pr^{III} complexes with glycine, L-glutamine and L-asparagine in order to determine the effects of sizes and steric hindrances of amino acids on the solution stability of the complexes.

Experimental

A.R. grade chemicals were used. The concentrations of metal, potassium chloride and gelatin in the test solution were 2.0 mM, 1.0 M and 0.01% respectively. A pH of 2.40 ± 0.1 was adjusted with dilute solutions of sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid, and was measured on a LI-10 needle type pH meter. Current-voltage measurements were made on a manual polarograph using a Toshniwal